

HOW EFFECTIVE IS TECHNOLOGICAL TRAINING IN A HEIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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ABSTRACT

The development of information technology allows program developers to introduce innovations into the education system. Technology changes are happening so quickly that it is estimated that 55% of training programs are based on computer technology. Attitude is a necessary condition for the result so that every person can succeed in any educational program. It is necessary to identify the needs that contribute to improving the effectiveness of training.

The entry of digital technologies into the educational environment not only complements the traditional education system, but also significantly expands the channels for transmitting knowledge and culture. We are talking, first of all, about global educational platforms such as Coursera and the National Open Education Platform, which today are the main channels for the electronic distribution of educational courses. The modern world, being digital, necessitates the use of digital technologies in education, primarily in the context of self-study based on online courses, among which massive open online courses occupy a significant place.

Massive open online courses are an educational technology that allows organizing training for up to several tens of thousands of people simultaneously. Equating the spread of massive open online courses to the Gutenberg revolution, the rector of the Higher School of Economics Y. Kuzminov writes: "... the emergence of online courses can be compared with the transition from copying books in medieval monasteries to their mass printing, so they make it more economical and the task of transmitting quality educational content is more effective" [3].

Experience shows that students' socio-demographic factors, such as age, academic performance and work experience, influence their attitudes towards learning. The influence of demographic factors is recognized by Karuppan in his study of Internet user profile. Computers are more effective for low-performing students, and there are no gender differences in the effectiveness of computer applications [2].

Students develop more positive attitudes towards learning. But there are students who are not confident computer users and they will encounter obstacles. In school education, the introduction of computers has led to an improvement in students' attitudes towards school and subjects. Features such as personalized programs, interactivity, multimedia elements, and

textual criticism are important for effective and engaging educational materials. The term textual criticism in the context of information technology-based learning refers to the way words or text are displayed on a computer screen. For example, Sambrook, in a study of factors influencing student perceptions of the quality of computer materials, identified the following important factors:

- ✓ user friendliness;
- ✓ presentation, graphics, information, knowledge, comprehension, level, type of learning, language and text.

According to Chambers and Sprecher, the main principles for developing effective training programs are: interactivity and individualization, the use of multimedia elements, textual criticism and learning systems [1].

Seven characteristics of interactivity were identified: responsiveness, varied access to information, adaptability, feedback, options, bidirectional communication, and the ability to learn at your own time. Individual training is recognized as an effective teaching method. Individual programs allow the student to control the pace and initial level of mastering educational materials.

Multimedia refers to the use of multiple media elements such as text, graphics, motion, voice, sound, animation and digital video. The use of sound and graphics makes learning materials easier to understand.

To summarize, we emphasize that innovations in education are associated with the informatization of society and the technologization of the educational process. First of all, they transform the means and methods of teaching, the system of communication between participants in the educational process, expand the channels of reproduction and transmission of information, excluding the personal participation of a person from these processes. Thanks to them, the possibility of distance learning, the use of online courses, and the creation of

educational platforms that present electronic courses have become possible. At the same time, the means and methods of learning, based on the psychological and physiological processes of human thinking, such as perception, understanding, memorization, reflection, are quite stable. They are necessary in any educational systems, both traditional and innovative, as is the use of traditional teaching methods in modern higher education. Thus, it is possible to fully use educational materials of computer technology and classroom training. When conducting training courses, the teacher can use the curriculum to present some ideas that will make it easier for people to continue learning. This may create a mutual benefit between computer training and classroom training, as both types of training have their own strengths and weaknesses.

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